

Impact of Triarchic Personality Traits on Cyberbullying Perpetration: Mediating Role of Attitudes Towards Cyberbullying

Kainat Umar, Saira Khan, Kainat Zia, Hamna Tehniyyat, Inayat Shah

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 20, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: August 21, 2024</p> <p>Keywords : Triarchic Personality Traits, Cyberbullying, Attitudes towards Cyberbullying</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13355746</p>	<p><i>This study examines the complex links between personality factors, cyberbullying attitudes, and cyberbullying in Pakistani culture. Triarchic psychopathy features are added to Barlett and Gentile's theory in the research. The study first establishes the factor structure of the Triarchic Psychopathy Scale, Cyberbullying Scale, ICT Self-Efficacy Scale, Attitude Towards Cyberbullying Scale, and Cyberbullying-specific Moral Disengagement Questionnaire in Pakistani culture. The confirmatory factor analyses on these scales show adequate data fit with appropriate factor loadings and internal consistencies. After that, Pearson product correlations confirm the link between triarchic psychopathy and cyberbullying. Multiple regression study shows meanness and boldness positively predict cyberbullying. Harmful attitudes regarding cyberbullying explain a large percentage of the connections between these personality qualities and cyberbullying perpetration, emphasizing the importance of attitudes in understanding how personality features affect cyberbullying. Disinhibition, another personality trait, does not correlate with negative cyberbullying attitudes, suggesting a more complex relationship between personality traits and attitudes. General cyberbullying characteristics moderate the associations between meanness, boldness, and cyberbullying perpetration, emphasizing their usefulness in cyberbullying prevention strategies. This study helps explain cyberbullying in Pakistani culture and underlines the necessity for culturally appropriate solutions.</i></p>

Introduction

Today's internet and social media have changed how people communicate. These technological advances have brought numerous benefits, but cyberbullying has become a major issue. Cyberbullying includes sending nasty messages, spreading rumors, and posting embarrassing content (Hinduja & Patchin, 2018). This is especially concerning for teens and young adults, who make up many internet platform users. Cyberbullying is rising, endangering this group's mental and emotional well-being (Hinduja & Patchin, 2020). To understand the causes of such harmful behavior, Patrick, Lilienfeld, and Benning's (2014) Triarchic Psychopathy Model is useful. This model defines psychopathy as Boldness, which includes social dominance, fearlessness, and a desire for thrilling experiences; Meanness, which includes aggression, callousness, and manipulative behavior; and Disinhibition, which includes impulsivity, poor self-regulation, and a lack of restraint. The Triarchic model has been debated in psychology, but it offers a comprehensive perspective on how different combinations of these features can manifest in individuals.

Scholars are now studying Triarchic personality features and cyberbullying. People are increasingly aware that their views on cyberbullying affect their participation in it. Positive perspectives of cyberbullying, such as viewing it as fun or a way to gain social recognition, have been linked to increased cyberbullying (Barlett & Coyne, 2014). These viewpoints and Triarchic personality qualities like Meanness or Disinhibition may increase cyberbullying. Recent studies have enhanced our comprehension of the relationship between personality traits and cyberbullying within various cultural frameworks. For example, Zheng et al. (2019) performed research involving Chinese adolescents, discovering that diminished levels of agreeableness and conscientiousness were notably linked to increased instances of cyberbullying perpetration. This investigation emphasizes the influence of personality traits on online aggressive conduct and indicates that these associations may differ across cultural settings. In a similar vein, Baldry, Sorrentino, and Farrington (2019) examined the effects of moral disengagement and personality traits on cyberbullying among Italian adolescents, finding that moral disengagement, when coupled with callous-unemotional characteristics (akin to the Meanness dimension), significantly heightened the risk of engaging in cyberbullying. These results underscore the necessity of considering the interplay between personality traits and cognitive elements such as moral reasoning in the analysis of cyberbullying (Fraga, Martins, Silva & Cruz, 2022).

Poon and Chen (2019) found that narcissism—a Boldness dimension personality trait—predicts cyberbullying among Malaysian teenagers. This study shows how cultural differences might affect online personality expression, especially in non-Western environments. These findings suggest that personality qualities influence cyberbullying, emphasizing the need to address cultural factors. Cyberbullying has increased in Pakistan due to rapid digital technologies and youth social media use. However, Pakistan's cultural and social factors, such as collectivist principles, religious beliefs, and societal expectations, may influence people's perceptions of cyberbullying and their likelihood of engaging in it. Pakistani culture values family honor and reputation, hence people may engage in cyberbullying to protect or improve their social status. Pakistani studies are revealing the prevalence and effects of youth cyberbullying. According to Ali, Khan, and Shah (2019), Pakistani teenagers are victims of cyberbullying, which causes psychological and emotional anguish. Khalid, Khalid, and Amin (2021) examined the relationship between personality traits and cyberbullying among Pakistani college students, finding that Triarchic model personality traits predict cyberbullying. Given Pakistan's growing concern about cyberbullying and its potential negative effects on youth mental health, a study into its causes is crucial. This study examines the association between Triarchic personality traits and cyberbullying among Pakistani adolescents and young adults, highlighting the mediating role of attitudes. Effective preventative and intervention efforts need to understand how these personality traits and attitudinal factors interact in Pakistan's cultural and social context. This study may illuminate the complex causes of youth cyberbullying in Pakistan. This study can help create culturally appropriate interventions and educational programs to improve online safety and empathy in youth by identifying the personality traits and attitudes that contribute to cyberbullying. In an increasingly interconnected world, such programs will help Pakistani young develop the skills to responsibly and respectfully use digital spaces, improving their well-being and mental health.

Methodology

Research Design & Sample

Participants

The sample size for the pilot study was 50. The data ($n = 496$) for the current study has been collected from the students at schools, colleges, and universities in the Twin Cities. The sample age ranged from 11 years to 22 years with $M = 18.30$ years, $SD = \pm 1.58$. Permission from the guardians was obtained to approach minors (adolescents under 16 years of age) and to involve them in the present study. The inclusion criteria for the current study were the students who could use the internet and have access to mobile phones and social media networking sites, as well as adolescents who could comprehend the items of the questionnaires. In this study, purposive sampling method was used.

Instruments

Triarchic Psychopathy Measure; The triarchic psychopathy model—Boldness, Meanness, and Disinhibition—has been recognized (Hyatt et al., 2020). Boldness involves risk-taking and reduced emotional responsiveness, meanness involves cold-heartedness and lack of empathy (Frick & Marsee, 2019; Lynam et al., 2019), and disinhibition involves impulsivity and recklessness, affecting both external and internal behaviors. The Triarchic Psychopathy Measure (TriPM) is commonly used to measure these qualities (Patrick, 2010). We used a reduced 15-item version with three subscales: Meanness (1-5), Boldness (6-10), and Disinhibition (11-15). The 4-point scale ranged from 0 (false) to 3 (true). The reliability values for each subscale were: Boldness $\alpha = .80$, Meanness $\alpha = .78$, and Disinhibition $\alpha = .70$.

Cyberbullying; It is any conduct using electronic or digital media by individuals or organizations that continuously send hostile or aggressive messages to injure or distress others (Tokunaga, 2010). Higher cyberbullying ratings indicate cyberbullies and vice versa (Musharraf, 2020). The current study used the English Cyberbullying scale (Musharraf, 2020). The scale has 20 items. Choose from (0) "Never" to (4) "More times a week". Cyberbullying frequency was asked in the "past 12 months". The final score was the sum of all one-way scores. Scale alpha reliability is 0.83.

Attitudes Towards Cyberbullying; Individuals' attitudes are liabilities or inclinations to behave a certain manner (Fishbein & Ajzen, 2007). Psychoticism and extraversion are linked to cyberbullying attitudes in

this study (Suriyabandara, 2017). Higher positive attitudes towards cyberbullying questionnaire scores reflect pro-cyberbullying attitudes (Barlett et al., 2016). The positive cyberbullying attitude scale (Barlett et al., 2016) measures attitudes. This survey has nine questions. The scale measures harmful cyberbullying attitudes (HCA) and general cyberbullying characteristics. HCA has 5 elements, 1–5, and GCC has 6–9. Participants were asked to rate the items from 1 = “Strongly Disagree” to 5 = “Strongly Agree”. Scale internal consistency is 0.71 for HCA and 0.64 for GCC. Alpha dependability of the entire scale is $\alpha = 0.71$.

Procedure

This study is quantitative, correlational, and cross-sectional. The authors gave email permission to use scales. To collect sample data, an informed consent form, demographic sheet, and study tools were included in a booklet. Before filling out surveys, participants were instructed on the study. Questions about the questionnaire and research goal were answered and participants were asked to answer accurately. Every scale's reliability was calculated. The demographic sheet now asks about age, gender, education system, present inhabitants, parental online monitoring, and cyberbullying. Scales were employed to measure conceptual mode variables and hypothesis relationships. Finally, participants were thanked for their time and responses. To finish, SPSS software was used to enter the data. Calculations were made to correlate study variables.

Results

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics of the variables ($N = 496$)

Demographics	<i>N</i>	%
Gender		
Male	244	49.2
Female	252	50.8
Age		
Middle Adolescence	308	62.1
Late Adolescence	188	37.9
Educational Level		
Primary	17	3.4
Secondary	224	45.2
Tertiary	255	51.4

In Table 1; the distribution suggests that middle adolescents (62.1%) outnumbered late adolescents. Primary-level adolescents were scarce compared to secondary and university students. Gender and education system frequencies were not significantly different throughout the sample (Hyes, 2013).

Table 2 Cronbach's Alpha and Descriptive Statistics of Scales and Subscales ($N = 496$)

Variables	<i>K</i>	α	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Range		Skewness	Kurtosis
					Potential	Actual		
Meanness	5	.88	5.09	3.04	0-15	1-13	.74	-.23
Boldness	5	.87	5.29	2.94	0-15	2-13	.95	.00
Disinhibition	5	.81	5.87	3.05	0-15	2-13	.65	-.70
CBS	20	.97	31.63	13.37	20-100	20-75	1.46	1.22
HCA	5	.85	9.59	4.93	5-25	5-25	1.10	.48
GCC	4	.80	9.37	4.36	4-20	4-20	.52	-.63

Note. *M* = Mean; *SD* = Standard Deviation; CBS = Cyberbullying Scale; HCA = Harmful Cyberbullying Attitudes; GCC = General Cyberbullying Characteristics.

Reliabilities, Mean, Range, Skewness, and Kurtosis of the study variables are shown in Table 2. The most common Cronbach's alpha is .70 or higher (Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson, & Tatham, 2006). Table 15 shows that all measurements have α -values above .70. A table shows Means and Standard Deviations. Low to high standard deviation values indicate that responses are spread from each variable's mean. The actual and potential ranges reveal that all scores fall within the potential ranges. The scale descriptions were consistent. Skewness and kurtosis evaluate the normal distribution. The table indicates that all scales have skewness and kurtosis between -2 and +2. This range proves normal distribution, allowing parametric tests (George & Mallery, 2010). Parametric tests can examine data with all values within normal ranges.

Table 3 Correlations of the study variables ($N = 496$)

Sr. No	Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	Meanness	-	.61**	.66**	.23**	.16**	.16**
2	Boldness		-	.45**	.16**	.12**	.14**

3	Disinhibition	-	.21**	.08	.09
4	CBS		-	.33**	.21**
5	HCA			-	.73**
6	GCC				-

Note. CBS = Cyberbullying Scale; HCA = Harmful Cyberbullying Attitudes; GCC = General Cyberbullying Characteristics.

Current study variables' correlation coefficients are shown in Table 3. Meanness positively correlates with boldness, disinhibition, cyberbullying, detrimental cyberbullying attitudes, and general cyberbullying characteristics. Meanness, aggressiveness, and cyberbullying attitudes are positively correlated with disinhibition. Cyberbullying is positively correlated with harmful attitudes and traits. General and harmful cyberbullying attitudes are highly positively correlated.

Table 4 Multiple Regression Analysis for the Effect of Meanness, Boldness, Disinhibition, ICT Self-Efficacy, Attitudes Towards Cyberbullying, and Moral Disengagement on Cyberbullying Perpetration (N = 496)

Variable	B	SE	β	95% CI		p
				LL	UL	
CBS	25.60***	3.09		19.54	31.67	.00
Meanness	.73*	.28	.17	.19	1.28	.01
Boldness	-.13	.23	-.03	-.59	.33	.57
D	.51*	.24	.12	.05	.98	.03
HCA	.86***	.16	.32	.55	1.18	.00
GCC	-.17	.18	-.06	-.53	.18	.34
R ²	.21***					
F	18.51***					

Note. B = Unstandardized Coefficient; SE = Standard Error, CI = Confidence Interval; LL = Lower Limit; UL = Upper Limit; CBS = Cyberbullying Scale; HCA = Harmful Cyberbullying Attitudes; GCC = General Cyberbullying Characteristics; *** $p < .001$, * $p < .05$.

Table 4 shows the impact of meanness, boldness, and disinhibition. The value of R² .24 revealed that the predictors explained 24% variance in the outcome variable with F = 25.95, $p < .001$. The findings illustrated that meanness ($\beta = .17$, $p < .001$), disinhibition ($\beta = .12$, $p > .05$), and harmful cyberbullying attitudes ($\beta = .32$, $p < .001$) positively predicted cyberbullying. Whereas, Boldness ($\beta = -.03$, $p > .05$) and general cyberbullying characteristics ($\beta = -.06$, $p < .001$), negatively predicted cyberbullying.

Mediation Analysis

After testing direct relationships between variables, harmful cyberbullying attitudes, general cyberbullying characteristics, and cyberbullying-specific moral disengagement were tested as mediators for various relationships.

Harmful Cyberbullying attitudes as a mediator. Harmful cyberbullying attitudes were analyzed as a mediator in the prediction of cyberbullying by meanness and boldness. The findings showing the mediating role of harmful cyberbullying attitudes in the relationship between meanness, boldness, and cyberbullying have been presented in Table 5.

Table 5 Mediation of Harmful Cyberbullying Attitudes between Meanness and Cyberbullying Perpetration (N=496)

Variable	Model 1	Model 2	SE	95% CI	
	β	β		LL	UL
Constant	26.38***	19.63***	1.44	16.79	22.46
Meanness	1.03**	.82***	.18	.45	1.18
HCA		.82***	.11	.59	1.04
R ²	.05	.14			
ΔR^2		.09			
F	28.72***	41.21***			
ΔF^2		12.49			

Note. HCA = Harmful Cyberbullying Attitudes; *** $p < .001$

Table 5 reveals that harmful cyberbullying attitudes mediate meanness and cyberbullying. Models 1 and 2 showed that meanness has a significant total influence on cyberbullying, while Model 2 showed that meanness has a significant direct effect after controlling for detrimental cyberbullying attitudes. Additionally, meanness significantly mediated cyberbullying perpetration through detrimental attitudes ($\beta = .21$, 95% CI = .07, .37), explaining a 9% variance in cyberbullying.

Figure 1. Path Diagram for Mediation Analysis

The unstandardized regression coefficients for meanness, hazardous cyberbullying attitudes, and cyberbullying are shown in Figure 1. Cyberbullying grows with meanness, as shown by the direct channel. Meanness increases dangerous cyberbullying attitudes, as seen by the strongly favorable indirect path. Thus, meanness indirectly reduces cyberbullying by improving harmful cyberbullying attitudes. This supports the second hypothesis that meanness increases cyberbullying and detrimental cyberbullying attitudes.

Next, Table 6 shows how negative cyberbullying attitudes mediate boldness-cyberbullying relationships.

The table shows how bad cyberbullying attitudes mediate boldness and cyberbullying. The total effect of boldness on cyberbullying is considerable as explained by Model 1 and Model 2, and the direct effect is significant when adjusting for detrimental cyberbullying attitudes. Additionally, meanness significantly mediated cyberbullying perpetration through detrimental attitudes ($\beta = .16$, 95% CI = .02, .33), explaining a 10% variance in cyberbullying. Figure 2 shows the meanness-based cyberbullying prediction model based on these findings.

Unstandardized regression coefficients for boldness, harmful cyberbullying attitudes, and cyberbullying are shown in Figure 2. The straight pathway shows that boldness encourages cyberbullying. The strongly positive indirect path reveals that boldness increases detrimental cyberbullying attitudes and cyberbullying.

Table 6 Mediation of Harmful Cyberbullying Attitudes Between Boldness and Cyberbullying Perpetration (N=496)

Variable	Model 1	Model 2	SE	95% CI	
	β	β		LL	UL
Constant	27.89***	20.52***	1.52***	17.53	23.52
Boldness	.71***	.54**	.19***	.15	.92
HCA		.86***	.86***	.63	1.08
R^2	.02	.12			
ΔR^2		.10			
F	12.18***	34.68***			
ΔF^2		22.5			

Note. HCA = Harmful Cyberbullying Attitudes; ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Boldness indirectly affects cyberbullying by improving detrimental cyberbullying attitudes. Boldness increases cyberbullying and detrimental cyberbullying attitudes, supporting the second hypothesis. The correlation study showed no significant link between disinhibition and hazardous cyberbullying attitudes (Table 6).

Figure 2. Indirect Effect of Boldness on Cyberbullying Perpetration through Harmful Cyberbullying Attitude

**General
Cyberbullying Characteristics as a Mediator**

An analysis of general cyberbullying characteristics as a mediator was carried out in the relationship between meanness and cyberbullying which yielded significant results.

Table 7 Mediation of General Cyberbullying Characteristics Between Meanness and Cyberbullying Perpetration(N=496)

Variable	Model 1	Model 2	SE	95% CI	
	β	β		LL	UL
Constant	26.38***	21.88***	1.56	18.80	24.96
Meanness	1.03***	.90***	.19	.53	1.28
GCC		.54***	.13	.28	.81
R^2	.05	.08			
ΔR^2		.03			
F	28.72***	23.26***			
ΔF^2		5.46			

Note. GCC = General Cyberbullying Characteristics; ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Table 7 indicates how general cyberbullying features mediate meanness and perpetration. The total effect of meanness on cyberbullying is significant as explained by Model 1 and Model 2, and the direct effect is significant when allowing for generic cyberbullying features. Additionally, meanness significantly mediated cyberbullying perpetration through detrimental attitudes ($\beta = .16$, 95% CI = .02, .33), explaining a 3% variance in cyberbullying.

Figure 3. Indirect Effect of Meanness on Cyberbullying Perpetration through General Cyberbullying Characteristics

Unstandardized regression coefficients for meanness, general cyberbullying traits, and cyberbullying are shown in Figure 3. Cyberbullying grows with meanness, as shown by the direct channel. A statistically positive indirect path reveals that meanness increases cyberbullying by raising generic cyberbullying traits. Thus, meanness indirectly strengthens cyberbullying by improving general cyberbullying traits. Meanness increases cyberbullying and general cyberbullying features, supporting the third hypothesis. Next, Table 8 shows how general cyberbullying qualities mediate boldness-cyberbullying relationships.

Table 8 Mediation of General Cyberbullying Characteristics between Boldness and Cyberbullying Perpetration(N=496)

Variable	Model 1	Model 2	SE	95% CI	
	B	β		LL	UL
Constant	27.89***	22.97***	1.63	19.75	26.19
Boldness	.71***	.58***	.20	.18	.97
GCC		.59***	.13	.33	.86
R^2	.02	.06			
ΔR^2		.04			
F	12.18***	16.04***			
ΔF^2		3.86			

Note. GCC = General Cyberbullying Characteristics; *** $p < .001$

The table shows how general cyberbullying qualities mediate boldness and cyberbullying. The total effect of boldness on cyberbullying is significant as explained by Model 1 and Model 2, and the direct effect is significant when allowing for general cyberbullying characteristics. Additionally, meanness significantly mediated cyberbullying perpetration through general characteristics ($\beta = .12$, 95% CI = .03, .24), explaining a 4% variation. Figure 4 shows the meanness-based cyberbullying prediction model based on these findings.

Figure 4. Indirect Effect of Boldness on Cyberbullying Perpetration through General Cyberbullying Characteristics

Unstandardized regression coefficients for boldness, general cyberbullying features, and cyberbullying are shown in Figure 7. The straight pathway shows that boldness encourages cyberbullying. The strongly favorable indirect path suggests that boldness increases general cyberbullying characteristics and cyberbullying. Thus, boldness indirectly reduces cyberbullying by improving overall cyberbullying traits. The fourth hypothesis (boldness increases cyberbullying and general cyberbullying traits) is supported by this study.

Discussion

The designed study utilized an independent sample to determine the factor structure of some key scales like Cyberbullying, Attitude towards Cyberbullying, ICT Self-Efficacy, Cyberbullying-specific Moral Disengagement Questionnaire (CBMDQ), and Triarchic Psychopathy Scale, the aim was to confirm the rationality and reliability of this measurement standard in a specific cultural setting in Pakistan. In Phase II of the research, the key focus of the study was set to examine the fact that triarchic psychopathy behaviors, cyberbullying attitudes, ICT self-efficacy, and disengagement of cyberbullying impact cyberbullying penetration. With triarchic psychopathy traits being involved in this study, we determined its significant influence on cyberbullying and its outcomes. Phase II is primarily based on the theoretical framework of Barlett and Gentile. The framework is proven to be effective in explaining the roles of personality, attitude, ICT self-efficacy, and moral disengagement toward increased or decreased cyberbullying behavior (Zych, Baldry & Farrington, 2021; Lopes & Francisco, 2021).

Addressing the initial objectives defined, AMOS V.26 was used to conduct the factor structure confirmation of the mentioned scales. To determine which model fits the data perfectly, the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) was used as a primary index along with Comparative Fit Index (CFI) and Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) as supporting one. In the results, the Cyberbullying Scale was found to be the most appropriate scale to use in the Pakistani setting and environment as it was the scale that fitted the data. Meanwhile, other scales like the Cyberbullying Attitude Scale and Triarchic Psychopathy Measure required some covariance to be added to make them fit the given data. The indices indicated that the mentioned scales were valid and reliable fulfilling the main purpose of the study. Furthermore, the factor loadings for each scale met the criteria of being acceptable henceforth supporting the structuring reliability of scales.

To evaluate the internal consistency of each scale, Cronbach's alpha was used which ranged between the values of .80 to .97 indicating the satisfactory internal consistency of all scales. These findings aligned with the expected results in psychometric research where high internal consistency indicated that items within a scale measure the same primary construct. Additionally, Pearson product-moment correlations were utilized to explore the relationship between variables. The correlations were found to be in the expected directions and were consistent with the previous research thereby validating the existing findings. One notable finding was the positive relationship between cyberbullying perpetration and triarchic psychopathy traits that aligned with the existing link of psychopathic traits with callousness, impulsivity, and aggressive online behaviors (Guarneri, Paciello, & Giammarco, 2022; Machimbarrena et al., 2020).

In addition to all this, multiple regression analyses were employed to recognize the significant cyberbullying behavior predictors. Aligned with recent research, hostile and aggressive traits are one of the driving traits in increasing cyberbullying behavior (Ciucci et al., 2020; Leduc, Langelier, & Dumont, 2021). Similarly, meanness also emerged as one of the positive predictors of cyberbullying behavior. Another finding suggested that positive reinforcements of mean attitudes justified their cyberbullying therefore resulting in increased engagement in such behaviors (Lambe, Hudson, Craig & Pepler, 2017).

Limitations:

While comprehensive, the study contains limitations that should be addressed when interpreting the data. Eight Punjab and Islamabad schools, colleges, and universities provided data. The sample was large and representative of the local population, but the results may not apply to institutions in other provinces of Pakistan or to unschooled teenagers. The study's cross-sectional design also makes causal inferences between triarchic psychopathy traits, cyberbullying attitudes, and cyberbullying perpetration difficult. Self-reported data may create response biases because individuals may underreport or overreport behaviors or attributes.

Future Directions:

Future research should aim to address these limitations by employing a more diverse and geographically representative sample that includes participants from all four provinces of Pakistan. This would enhance the generalizability of the findings and provide a more comprehensive understanding of cyberbullying across different cultural and regional contexts in the country. Additionally, conducting longitudinal studies

would offer valuable insights into how triarchic psychopathy traits interact with various risk and protective factors over time. Long-term follow-ups could help identify potential developmental trajectories and shed light on how these traits manifest and evolve across different life stages. Furthermore, future studies might consider incorporating multi-method approaches, such as using behavioral observations or reports from peers and teachers, to mitigate the limitations associated with self-reported data. This approach would provide a more holistic understanding of the dynamics of cyberbullying and the factors influencing its occurrence.

Conclusion

The current study provides valuable insights into the relationship between triarchic psychopathy traits and cyberbullying perpetration, as well as the mediating effects of attitudes towards cyberbullying. The findings indicate that meanness and disinhibition positively predict cyberbullying perpetration, while boldness shows a weak positive association. Moreover, harmful cyberbullying attitudes and general cyberbullying characteristics act as significant predictors of cyberbullying perpetration, partially mediating the relationship between meanness, boldness, disinhibition, and cyberbullying.

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Author Information

Kainat Umar

NIP, Quaid-e-Azam University, Islamabad, Pakistan

Saira Khan

NIP, Quaid-e-Azam University, Islamabad, Pakistan

Kainat Zia

Department of Psychology, University of Malakand, KP, Pakistan

Hamna Tehniyyat

Sheffield Health & Social Care, UK

Inayat Shah

Department of Psychology, University of Malakand, KP, Pakistan